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CORPORATE GOVERNANCE: A CASE STUDY OF SATYAM AND TATA

Dr. G. C. Jaiswal*
Dharen Kumar Paudey**

Abstract

Market-oriented economy and increased cross-border transactions have augmented the importance of the law in the development of the nation. Corporate governance has, thus, evolved in order to safeguard the interests of the public in the management of the company's affairs. Good corporate governance, however, needs the firm's commitment in adopting ethical practices while dealing with all its stakeholders in the global prospective. Developing economies like India, still suffers with many issues regarding the corporate governance. There is a need for implementing globally accepted standards and principles for monitoring corporate activities in order to achieve the overall objective of corporate governance. Corporate governance is a necessity for long-term sustainability. Key Words: Corporate Governance, Market-oriented, Cross-border, Standards, Principles.

Corporate Governance: A Case study of satyam and tata

Introduction

"Corporate Governance can be a laboratory for good political governance in India."- Mr. Salman Khursid (Minister of Corporate Affairs)

Corporate is the engine for the growth and development of the economy. It provides employment, goods, services, and infrastructure to the economy. Globalisation has increased the role of the corporate and also inhabited it with many responsibilities to be concerned while performing its activities. Corporate governance is thus an international call for the companies. Corporate governance is a broad term which has no bounded definition yet. In general, it is referred as the laws, policies and rules under which management decisions are finalised in a corporate body. The term corporate governance can be divided into two: Corporate, derived from the Latin word "corporatus" meaning 'to make into a body' and, Governance, derived from the Greek word "kubernao" meaning 'to steer'. Thus, it can be said that corporate governance is an activity of governing the corporate organisations, i.e., to set rules and byelaws under which all the activities of the corporate bodies must operate. It is just like keeping eye over every activity of the corporate bodies so that no one is deceived or victimised by their decision. Now the question occurs, who will govern and within what limits? The simple answer to this question is that in this globalised era there must be a globally and mutually accepted set of principles, rules and byelaws which would monitor whether all the activities are under the prescribed code of conduct. It becomes the social responsibility of each and every corporate body to

abide by the rules and byelaws formulated for the purpose of corporate governance. In short, corporate governance calls for five basic codes to be minded by the corporate: accountability, efficiency & effectiveness, integrity & fairness, responsibility, and transparency.

The major issues responsible for the call for corporate governance in India were the downfall of many big investments, the increase in executives' compensation package, downsizing in all the sectors, securities scams, and the hostile takeovers and the corporate restructuring practices. Company law, securities laws, five year plans, industrial policy resolutions, licencing and development finance institutions were the majors in the corporate governance in India until 1990s, when the Confederation of Indian Industry took the first initiative in 1996 in this perspective with the objective to develop and promote a code for corporate governance to be adopted by Indian companies. The National Task Force was set which declared the Desirable Corporate Governance Code in April, 1997. The major securities market scam in 1992 by the mastermind Harshad Mehta, forced the Government to provide powers to the Securities and Exchange Board of India which then issued strict corporate governance norms for public companies. SEBI further imposed Clause 49 in February 2000, to be implemented by the firms. The major constituents of the Clause 49 were the power to the independent directors, the term of office of non-executive directors, code of conduct for the Board, subsidiary companies, disclosures and certifications. Moreover, the Ministry of Company Affairs have been named as the Ministry of Corporate

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Affairs. Recently the new accounting system, the IFRS system, has been implemented by the Ministry of Corporate Affairs so that Indian Corporate is at par with Global Companies. Wipro Limited is the first company to be fully integrated with the new IFRS accounting system. The Ministry of Corporate Affairs is also planning to implement the XBRL system for reporting. According to the press release by the Ministry of Corporate Affairs, the report of the Parliamentary Standing Committee on Finance on the Companies Bill 2009 has been submitted and the New Companies Act is to be enacted by the end of this financial year. It now seems that these initiatives will definitely lead to a balanced corporate governance practice in India.

Literature Review

The concept of corporate governance has always been a big issue for researchers. Different scholars have different views about corporate governance. Zingales (1998) and Williamson (1985) have similar view about corporate governance. They have considered it as "the complex set of constraints that shape the ex-post bargaining over the quasi-rents generated by a firm". Garvey and Swan (1994) have considered the corporation as a tie between implicit and explicit contracts and emphasized that "governance determines how the firm's top decision makers (executives) actually administer such contracts". They have also observed that governance only matters when such contracts are incomplete, and that a consequence is that executives "no longer resemble the Marshallian entrepreneur". According to Shleifer and Vishny (1997) corporate governance "deals with the ways in which suppliers of finance to corporations assure themselves of getting a return on their investment". With a similar view, Caramanolis-Cotelli (1995) regards corporate governance as being determined by the equity allocation among insiders (including executives, CEOs, directors or other individual, corporate or institutional investors who are affiliated with management) and outside investors. Murthy (2006) finds that good corporate governance is a setup which maximise the shareholder's wealth legally, ethically and more transparently.

When we talk about the role of corporate governance, it is necessary in order to remove the mistrust level between the management and its stakeholders. Good corporate governance not only reduces legal costs and improves social and labour relations but also calls for the environmental protection. Good corporate governance also leads to good corporate value. Hart (1995) suggests that "corporate governance issues arise in an organisation whenever two conditions are present. First, there is an agency problem, or conflict of interest, involving members of the organisation – these might be owners, managers, workers or

consumers. Second, transaction costs are such that this agency problem cannot be dealt with through a contract". Corporate governance deals with mechanisms by which stakeholders of a corporation exercise control over corporate insiders and management such that their interests are protected (John and Senbet, 1998). More than 60 per cent of the investors are attracted towards corporate governance practices of a corporate while investment decisions (McKinsey, 2002).

Objective and methodology

The main objective of this paper is to discuss various issues in corporate governance in India. This paper also tries to discuss the concept of corporate governance. A case study of the Satyam Computer Services scam and Corporate Governance by Tata group is also included in this paper. The paper is theoretical and informative in nature. It has been completed by the use of secondary data available by the help of articles by eminent writers in different journals and electronic sources.

Corporate governance Mechanism in India

The corporate governance system in India is highly decentralised. The whole dynamics of corporate governance in India is administered by a number of laws, rules and policies by a number of statutory bodies, associations, institutes and the recommendations of various working committees designed for this purpose. The major regulators of corporate governance in India are the Ministry of Corporate Affairs and the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI). The guidelines are not uniform in nature. There have been many instances of conflict of interest between these two regulators regarding various concerned issues. An example of the regulatory overlaps in this regard among the above are regarding insider trading, number of individual directors, and delisting of publicly-traded companies. Besides this there are many issues which include constraints to participation in Annual General Meetings, the need for corporate governance code for unlisted companies, etc. The anatomy of corporate governance in India is not specific and it needs to be restructured with adequate responsibility to the regulators under their jurisdiction. The conflict in interest must be avoided in order to develop a good corporate governance structure in India. The World Bank Assessment, 2004 noticed that there was a lack of clarity in regard to the responsibility of corporate governance between the two regulators which had been weakening the enforcement of the corporate governance guidelines. It also emphasized that the institutional investors must also be encouraged in developing the code of conduct for the corporate governance. Hence, there is a necessity to restructure the corporate governance mechanism in India.

Issues in Corporate Governance

In this part we will deal with the major issues which have been the topic of discussion by many eminent authors in relation with the Indian corporate governance structure. Many of such issues include the ownership issue in Indian companies, the annual general meeting process, the voting process, corporate disclosures, business ethics being followed and scope of the law in all these regards.

One of the issues in corporate governance is the ownership of the corporate. Who really is the owner and who decides? Theories state that the shareholders are the actual owners of the company but the management is in the hands of the Board (as elected by the shareholders). Shareholders comprise of majority and minority shareholders. Majority shareholders are directly involved in management. Under the Board members, there are managers who are controlling the most of the important decisions of the business. There is a chance that the Board members may fulfil their interest first and then the interests of the other shareholders and there is even another chance where the managers may bag their own interest first. The question here is about the misuse of the powers by the management and the majority shareholders. The promoters (or the majority shareholders) of the corporate body may affect the interest of the minority shareholders. In short, we can say that corporate governance aims at minimising this misuse of power by the management and the majority shareholders. The Securities law in this respect has issued guidelines regarding the promoter's contribution and minimum lock in period. The promoters need to take a minimum of 20 per cent stake in the capital of the company and to retain these shares for a minimum lock in period of three years.

Another important issue in corporate governance is regarding the shareholder's meeting and voting rights. In India, many shareholders did not receive the notices for the meetings of the Board. Even the proceedings of the Annual General Meetings of the companies are rarely available in time. The Indian process of voting by the show of hands and especially, the proxy voting is very poor. The main drawback of this practice is the poor accountability and efficiency. In order to curb out this problem, details of every meeting must be available to the stakeholders, the proxies must be allowed to speak in meetings, and the voting must be through a poll. The practice of corporate disclosure in India is not healthy. There is a need for enhancing the scope of corporate disclosures and improve the limitations of corporate disclosure. The format of financial disclosures by Indian companies is totally different from those by the US companies. The accounting rules applied are inconsistent. The evaluation

pattern of the Indian corporate governance code is still ambiguous in this respect.

The Satyam scam: A Case Study

Satyam Computer Services (the fourth largest Indian IT company) was established in the year 1987 by B. Ramlinga Raju as a Private Limited Company. In the year 1991, it was recognized as a public limited company. It was listed on the BSE and its IPO was oversubscribed by 17 times. It was awarded ISO 9001 Certification in 1993. In the year 2000, it received the National HRD Award from the Indian Government. In 2001, it became the world's first ISO 9001:2000 Company to be certified by BVQI. It also got listed on the NYSE. Satyam BPO was launched in Hyderabad in 2002. It had set up the first "Global Innovation Hub" in Singapore in 2006. In 2007, it became the Official IT services provider for the FIFA World Cups, 2010 (South Africa) and 2014 (Brazil). It also became the first Asian company to feature in the Training Magazines' list of top 125 companies for learning. In 2008, it became the first company to launch secondary listing in Euronext Amsterdam under NYSE Euronext's new Fast Path process for cross listings in New York and Europe. What great milestones the Satyam Computer Services have achieved in the 21 years since establishment! But all went into vain, when the net worth of its shareholders came down to a negative of ` 278 crore from a positive value of ` 8529 crore. The MD and Chairman of Satyam Computer, Mr. Ramlinga Raju resigned from his post in January, 2009 accepting that he has done fraud in the books of the company. It lost 77 per cent of its value in the market. It was removed from the Nifty India and BSE Sensex. Satyam ADR in NASDAQ lost 99.89 per cent of its value.

The question may be about the fraud which took place. The Satyam scam was a case of enlarging the profits of the company by manipulating the figures in the balance sheet for several years. The major manipulations in the financial books included the following:

1. The cash and the bank balances of ` 5040 crore were not real.
2. Accrued interest of ` 376 crore was non-existent.
3. Liability of ` 1230 crore was understated.
4. Debtors of ` 490 crore were overstated.
5. Growth of Fixed deposits from ` 3.35 crore in 1998-99 to ` 3320.19 crore in 2007-08 was all fake.

In short, it was a plan to show huge profit in the company. According to Ramalinga Raju, he did all this in order to save the company from takeover threats and to maintain its clients. The books were audited by the external auditors Price Water House Coopers (one of the best accounting firm). The following steps were taken by the Satyam

Computer Services Ltd. Under the guidance of the law:

1. The Company Law Board, Government of India asked the company to appoint 10 nominees as directors of the company and to replace the current board members.
2. The Ministry of Corporate Affairs appointed three distinguished members to the new Board of Directors which included Mr. Deepak Parekh (Chairman of DHFC), Mr. Kiran Karnik (former President of NASSCOM), and Mr. C. Achuthan (Director at the NSE).
3. The Ministry of Corporate Affairs again appointed three additional members to the Board of Directors which included Mr. T. N. Manoharan (former President of the ICAI), Mr. Tarun Das (CII), and Mr. S Balakrishna Mainak (LIC). The foundation of the Board was now considered to be strong.
4. Goldman Sachs and Avendus were appointed as investment bankers.
5. Boston Consulting Group was appointed as management advisors.
6. Mr. A. S. Murthy was appointed as the CEO.
7. In February, 2009, the Company Law Board gave the authorization for increasing the size of authorized equity shares, to make preferential allotment of shares and to induct strategic investors into the company.
8. The SEBI approved the global competitive bidding process. This process was supervised by Justice S. P. Bharucha.
9. An application for delisting Satyam's ADS's from NYSE Euronext was filed.
10. Venturbay Consultants Private Ltd. (a subsidiary of Tech Mahindra Ltd.) was approved as the successful bidder to acquire a controlling stake in Satyam by the Company Law Board.
11. The company Law Board also ordered Tech Mahindra to appoint not more than 4 of its nominees as directors in the Company's board.
12. Mr. C. P. Gurnani was appointed as the CEO and Mr. S. Durga Shanker was appointed as the CFO of Mahindra Satyam (the new brand name for Satyam Computers).

Satyam computers is now merged with Mahindra and going on well. The inefficiency of Corporate Governance, however, comes into notice by the irony of the Golden Peacock Award which was given to the Satyam Computers for its excellence in corporate governance in the year 2008 by the World Council for Corporate Governance. Satyam was also rated as the company

with Best Corporate Governance Practices in 2006 and 2007 by the Investor Relations Global Rankings (IRGR). In the past, in the year 2002, it was awarded the Golden Peacock Award for its corporate governance by the Institute of Directors, New Delhi.

Corporate Governance by Tata

Tata! The name is enough, when we talk about corporate governance. The purpose of the Tata group is the development of the society, the community and the company. It aims at creating trust among the customers, employees, shareholders and the community. Integrity, understanding, excellence, unity and responsibility – the five corporate values of the Tata group bring its name at the pioneer in all respect. The Tata code of conduct consists of twenty-five clauses. The first clause itself shows the love for the nation. It covers the national interest indicating that every company of the Tata group will operate for the economic development of the nation and no business of the Tata group shall be such which will detriment the national interest of the country in which it would operate. The second clause covers the financial reporting and records which states that the records will fairly be maintained and audited and there will be no wilful misrepresentation of accounts. Any such act of misrepresentation will lead to the violation of the code. The third clause states that Tata group will promote and cooperate with the market competition and it will never use the trade restrictive or trade abusive practices which deteriorate the competition. The fourth clause clearly states that there will be no bifurcation in the employment process as regards to race, religion, sex, nationality, etc. Everyone will be provided equal chance for employment and Tata group will always comply with the labour laws. The fifth, sixth, a seventh and eighth clause of the Tata group calls for zero politics, zero corruption and zero pollution. It calls for transparency in rules and regulations. The ninth clause ensures quality products and services to the society. Clause 10-15 include the company's commitment towards the community, mutual co-ordination among the Group companies, public and third party representation norms, the Tata brand and the group policies in the interest of the public and the nation and not personal. The sixteenth clause ensures the enhancement of the shareholder's wealth. While the seventeenth clause promise for ethical performance by the company in all respect, the eighteenth clause ensures the government and the law that Tata group will always comply with all the laws and regulations applicable at every territory where it will operate. The nineteenth clause steers at the concurrent employment of its employees. Clause 20-24 calls for the ethical compliances by its employees in regards to the interest of the company in the areas of data confidentiality, assets

protection, conflict of personal and corporate interest, etc. At last the twenty-fifth clause makes itself responsible for the reporting of any unfair practice inside the company which comes under the violation of the code of conduct of the company as well as the law. Members of the Tata group including the employees are obliged to familiarise themselves with all applicable laws, company policies, procedures and work rules and to work in the interest of the company within the code prescribed.

The twenty-five clauses for corporate governance not only show the sincerity of the Tata group in this respect but also focus upon its view towards social integration. Tata have always been an example for cooperating with the requirements of the law and the government in the well-being of all its stakeholders. The name itself holds the alphabet "T" which symbolises 'quality' in all activities.

Conclusions and Suggestions

However, the bitter experience of the Satyam scam clearly depicts that the corporate governance code is a very difficult task said to be honestly complied with by all the corporates. There is need for generation of the feeling of social responsibility by everyone. However, the study of the initiatives by Tata for its corporate governance says that there is a need of self-realisation by each and every

corporate body to step forward in this respect. It is also worth stating that the first initiative towards corporate governance in India was taken by the industry (the CII which is an industry based and industry managed organisation) and not by the government or the law. No law can control fraud and deceptiveness but only the glows of social responsibility in each corporate can do so. The law and the government can direct for certain codes of conduct and also go for various auditing tasks for the corporates but it is impossible for them to have a close view of all the activities happening behind the curtain. Thus, the law and the government must call for a moral suasion. The corporate governance by the corporates not only physiquies its own image but also of the nation in which it operates. Just by maintaining the corporate governance norms, the responsibility of the corporates is not concluded but it ends only after the sense of corporate governance is felt and understood by all of its members. The companies must feel that this will lead to a development in the economy they operate and to make the economy favourable is in their hand.

"Corporate Social Responsibility is not a charity, and should be the culture of the company."

- Dr. R. Bandhopadhyay (Secretary, Ministry of Corporate Affairs)

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